

GENRE-STYLISTIC FEATURES OF I. YUSUPOV'S FOREWORD ARTICLES

Jaksulikova Dilnoza Alliyar qizi

Doctoral student of Karakalpak State University, Nukus, Karakalpakstan, Uzbekistan

jaksulikovadilniza@gmail.com

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Abstract. *The article examines the genre and stylistic nature of I. Yusupov's forewords as paratextual elements. It analyzes how these prefaces function as authorial manifestos, combining literary criticism with memoir and lyrical discourse to establish a strategic communicative link between the author, the text, and the reader.*

Keywords: *foreword, paratext, I. Yusupov, Karakalpak literature, authorial reflection.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается жанрово-стилистическая природа предисловий И. Юсупова как паратекстуальных элементов. Анализируется функционирование предисловий как авторских манифестов, сочетающих литературную критику с мемуарным и лирическим дискурсом для установления стратегической коммуникативной связи между автором, текстом и читателем.*

Ключевые слова: *предисловие, паратекст, И. Юсупов, каракалпакская литература, авторская рефлексия.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada I. Yusupov so'zboshilarining parateksual element sifatidagi janriy-uslubiy tabiati tadqiq etilgan. So'zboshilarning muallif manifesti sifatidagi vazifasi, adabiy tanqidning memuar va lirik diskurs bilan uyg'unlashuvi hamda muallif, matn va kitobxon o'rtasidagi kommunikativ aloqani o'rnatishdagi o'rni tahlil qilingan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *so'zboshi, paratekst, I. Yusupov, qoraqalpog'iston adabiyoti, muallif refleksiya.*

Introduction

The historical changes in literary genre forms are considered one of the most important issues in contemporary literary studies. Among the traditional forms of literary thought, the author's introduction (preface) has undergone a long evolutionary path, distinguished by its unique and rarely encountered diversity of forms of expression.

Literature review

The study relied on the works of scholars such as G. Genette, N. Basbanes, B. Bursov, M.M. Bakhtin, D.S. Likhachev and Q. Orazimbetov on paratext theory. These authors view the preface as a space that serves as a link between the text and the reader and where the author's image is formed. In the field of Karakalpak literary criticism, the research of Z. Shamuratova and I. Yusupov's creative credo, methods of creating artistic and publicistic images were analyzed. Additionally, the tradition of introduction in Turkic literature was comparatively examined based on B. Canter's work.

Research methodology

Paratextual analysis, lyrical discourse analysis and methods of authorial rhetoric were used in the article. The artistic-communicative relationship between the author and the reader was analyzed based on Bakhtin's theory and the text structure was analyzed based on Genette's

paratext concept. Elements of lyrical and memoir discourse were examined in determining the author's «I» and spiritual credo in the preface texts. A content analysis of I. Yusupov's prefaces was conducted, examining the interconnectedness of historical context, literary tradition and poetic reflection. As a result, the multifaceted nature of the foreword as a unique literary genre was revealed.

Results and discussion

Modern literary studies define the foreword as a «constant factor», an «eternal form expressing various attitudes towards a work or book» [1, p. 100].

Forewords are recognized as «the main element of the meaning-creating system» and they can be evaluated as the «broader designation» of the work [2, p. 39].

Furthermore, the foreword is considered one of the «framing sections» of the work. Along with the author's name, title, subtitle, dedication, epigraph, content and author's notes, it performs an «organizing function»: it gives the work a sense of completeness, strengthens its internal unity, demonstrates the author's presence in the work and indicates that it is aimed at a specific readership [3, p. 848]. At the same time, such framing elements should not be analyzed separately, but interconnectedly and in conjunction with the main text, as the functions they perform can be redistributed among them.

D.S. Likhachev defines the process of artistic «understanding» as follows: it is the process by which the author «hints» to the reader about the spirit and meaning of the work. «In art, the perceiver (listener, reader, spectator) creates together with the author or independently of him, but based on his methods» [4, p. 11]. M.M. Bakhtin describes the author as an «authoritative guide» for the reader, an «active leader who shows us reality» and emphasizes that «our activity is his activity» [5, p. 180].

When analyzing the author's introduction, it is necessary to consider M.M. Bakhtin's concept of dynamic and diverse relationships between the author, the protagonist and the reader as subjects of artistic reality. The foreword can simultaneously function in two fields of different nature – in the direct (pathos-filled) author's word and in the artistic word. This characteristic allows us to evaluate the author's foreword as a phenomenon of artistic consciousness, as «the state in which this consciousness manifests its essential features» [6, p. 219].

At this point, the question may arise whether the introduction and the foreword are the same. According to common definitions in literary studies, a foreword is a type of introductory text provided at the beginning of a book. Usually, in this section, the author shares their thoughts on the idea of their work, the reason for writing it, creative tasks and historical context.

The foreword is positioned independently of the main text, while the introduction is considered a part of the main body of the work. A foreword can be written not only by the author but also by a specialist or researcher. These characteristics define the clear difference between a foreword and an introduction: although the foreword stands «outside» the text, it aims to establish a meaningful connection between the work and the reader.

In literary studies, during genre analysis, the foreword is considered a paratextual element. The French literary scholar G. Genette describes paratext as the «border zone» between the text and the space outside it: it includes information such as the book title, author's name, as well as textual additions like forewords or introductions. According to Genette, paratext is not a boundary, but rather a «space» that influences the perception of the text, that is, a strategic field that enables the reader to correctly understand and interpret the work [7]. From this perspective,

the foreword serves as a bridge between the author and the work: it can reveal the essence of the work and provide the reader with guidance on how to approach the text.

The foreword has its own unique genre characteristics. As noted by US literary scholar N. Basbanes, «the foreword is a unique textual space in which the author can widely utilize their creative potential» [8, 84]. Since this space does not belong to the main work, it allows the author, regardless of the established rules within the literary tradition, to convey comprehensive thoughts and apply innovative rhetorical techniques. For example, forewords often contain specific forms such as genre annotations, participation in discussions and direct addresses to the reader. Basbanes also emphasizes the special role of the foreword in introducing the text: «The foreword performs the function of introducing the text - it presents the text, praises the patron, requests financial support, or otherwise determines the place of the work and the author's position in the public arena» [8, 85]. Thus, the foreword becomes a platform for public attention for the author and their work.

Another characteristic of the author's foreword is that it can be viewed as a lyrical or monologue appeal accompanied by the author themselves. For example, some forewords encompass episodes from the author's own life or exploratory stories, through which they strive to establish a deeper connection with the reader. For an author, a foreword is an opportunity to introduce themselves, their book and the previous projects or experiences that influenced them. This is a story about how the initial idea transformed into the existing book. Therefore, a foreword is a paratextual genre that allows the author to justify the form of their work and reveal its value.

Although the foreword genre has its place in world literature, there is little conceptual analysis in this field. In the history of Turkic peoples' literature, there is a tradition of «muqaddima» (translated from Arabic as «introduction»), which is similar to the foreword. For example, in his research, B. Kanter (2021) notes that the content of muqaddimas in Ottoman Divan literature reflects the author's cognitive mechanism and poetic orientation. He also describes muqaddimas as «epistemological, poetic and historical texts of literature and culture spanning hundreds of years» [9]. In this tradition, the foreword or its equivalent is considered not a simple introduction to a work, but a mirror of creative cultural civilization. In Turkish literature after the second half of the 19th century (the Tanzimat period), prefaces acquired the character of manifestos, proclaiming new literary trends and poetic directions.

According to the renowned Russian literary scholar B. Bursov, the forewords (introductions) and afterwords written for collections of works by some poets and writers, as well as for anthologies, are considered a type of critical article, one of the structural and complex genres of literary criticism [10]. Such texts aim to evaluate the author's work and reveal their poetic or prose perspective on a scientific and artistic basis.

Scholar Z. Shamuratova, who conducted research on the emergence and strengthening of Karakalpak literary criticism, notes that the genres of foreword and afterword began to appear in Karakalpak literature at the end of the 1940s, writing the following: «The emergence of various literary almanacs dedicated to different political events gave rise to the genres of introduction, foreword (or afterword). These not only provided recommendations but also described specific stages of literary historical development and set tasks for Soviet literature» [11, 124].

With the development of our fiction, these genres have improved considerably.

The first scholarly reflections on the forms and significance of forewords to collections are presented in the monograph «Evolution and Typology of Artistic Forms in Contemporary

Karakalpak Lyrics» by Doctor of Philological Sciences Q. Orazimbetov. The scholar divides the forewords to collections into two main forms:

1. Author's foreword.
2. Foreword by another person.

It is stated that these two forms are found in Karakalpak literature. The monograph also analyzes I. Yusupov's forewords [12, 162-164].

Thus, the foreword genre is a complex artistic-rhetorical phenomenon aimed not only at creating an introduction to a literary text but also at regulating the relationship between the author and the reader. It provides the complete cultural context of the book and demonstrates its paratextual meaning. Literary scholars often perceive the foreword not as a part of the main work, but as independent epigraphic or epitextual content. Therefore, the foreword genre is unique as a space of creative freedom and expression and belongs to an influential link of extra-textual communication.

Author's foreword

The problem of the essence of literary processes originated in ancient aesthetics and remains one of the most important and complex issues in literary theory to this day. One of the directions of research on this issue is the study of the analyses given by the author of this work regarding their own creative work and, in general, their creative activity. Such analyses were reflected through various types of texts: forewords and conclusions written by the author, articles, ego-documents (letters, diaries, memoirs), as well as internal commentaries that have become part of the artistic text and are subject to its rules.

The analysis of texts of this type requires addressing a number of theoretical and methodological issues: the content of the concept of «author's self», its relationship with the idea of the work and the communicative function of the author's comments.

The specificity of the author's interpretation of their work depends, first and foremost, on the genre characteristics of the commentary being made. At the same time, the author enriches the characteristics of a stable genre with unique content. One of the genres of authorial commentary is the foreword. As constitutive features of the preface, one can say that it expresses the author's intention or idea and addresses the reader (hidden or open), since the explanation given by the author is necessary to introduce the work to the reader or (if the work has been published) to clarify the questions that arose in it. In the preface, undoubtedly, an element of self-analysis (self-reflection) also appears, because here the author, in a certain sense, views their work as an «external observer.»

An author's foreword to their collection of works is a phenomenon that occurs after the author gains considerable experience in the literary field and has the opportunity to express opinions about the literary process and fiction, or after becoming one of the leaders of a particular national literature [12, 164].

In I. Yusupov's forewords to his collections, the uniqueness and nature of the art of poetry are discussed based on his many years of experience. The foreword titled «A Short Discourse on Poetry» [13, 5-10] is written with aesthetic skill.

In this preface, the author criticizes his poem «Comrade Teacher».

«Comrade Teacher» is the poet's first work in the poem genre. After the poem was published in the press in 1949, various interpretations and opinions about it began to emerge in our criticism.

«If I were to read this poem now and then», writes I. Yusupov, «some naive manifestations of its artistry, youthful anxiety, would shake my head. But the fiery passion of the young muse in the poem, the fervor of the young heart and the thunderous gallop of the young pen still fascinate me.»

In the work «A Short Discourse on Poetry», the author delves into his life's journey, reflecting on the nature of poetry, the poet's place in society and his inner world.

In the work, the author narrates the story on the first page and the main character is himself. The village of Azat, where he spent his childhood, his first teachers, the places where he received his education, the literary environment, his first poems, the times of meetings with students – all of this is depicted through concrete facts. The author realistically and effectively depicts his spiritual development, his poetic pursuits and the stages of his growth. Love for his homeland and literature is felt in every line.

The composition of the work is free, based on the flow of thought. Memories and reflections, concrete events and philosophical conclusions are intertwined. The author constantly questions themselves, their work and society. For him, it is important not only to recount the past, but also to understand the essence and content of poetry, to delve into the source of his poetic talent.

The author communicates directly with the reader. They compare the present with the past and reflect on the younger generation. They express their views on literature and books, as well as the explorations of young writers.

Poet Ibrayim Yusupov, in his foreword «Seeking a Path to Hearts», describes the poet's spiritual and creative nature, saying:

«The poet writes his whole life, reads and learns his whole life. The poet, having endured much hardship, sets his own path and for the rest of his life, he finds his fortune on the path he has charted» [5, 5-10].

These words signify the difficulties of the creative path and the pursuit of constant exploration and spiritual perfection. The poet is characterized as a figure who learns throughout life, draws lessons from every path and engages in ceaseless dialogue with their inner spirit.

Yusupov also reflects on literary works created during the Soviet era and their reception today. In his view, many artistic works born in this period no longer meet the aesthetic tastes of the current young generation. This phenomenon is not accidental but directly related to historical and political circumstances. During the Soviet ideological era, literature served an ideological function and works that did not glorify the party, communism and political figures were considered ideologically weak. Artistic mastery was relegated to second place. As a result, political lyrics with predominantly journalistic and didactic tones became widespread in poets' works.

Today, such works are viewed as historical literary heritage and fail to generate aesthetic interest among the new generation of readers. However, Yusupov's perspective on poetry, his assessment of literature in general and his reflections on the poetic traditions of the Karakalpak and Turkic peoples are of particular theoretical importance. His thoughts on this matter can serve as a valuable foundation for understanding the developmental patterns of national poetry and for analyzing the literary process from a historical and artistic perspective.

Conclusion

Ibrayim Yusupov's foreword made a significant contribution to the development of literary criticism and creative metatitil in Karakalpak literature. They serve not only as an

introduction but also as an author's manifesto, expressing the author's literary and philosophical conclusions, personal creative position and attitude towards a particular genre and style. In their forewords, they often delve into the inner spiritual world of a particular author, revealing their path to the art of words, their formation and their creative nature.

From this point of view, I. Yusupov's preface is valuable in terms of personality, evidence, creativity and identity.

Yusupov frequently employs the method of genre transformation in his forewords. That is, on the one hand, they are well-founded literary criticism and on the other hand, they are written in the form of memoirs, literary portraits and lyrical essays. This genre diversity also enriches its literary prefaces formally. Such structural complexity – filling a simple preface with artistic-cognitive, analytical content – introduces the reader to the spiritual world of the work.

Furthermore, in his forewords, I. Yusupov strives to deeply analyze the important concepts of literary theory (genre, style, image, artistic system, literary tradition, innovation). It should be noted that his research in this area elevated the theoretical level of Karakalpak literary studies to a new level.

Ibrayim Yusupov's forewords, along with literary analysis, are a creative phenomenon that has deepened national artistic thought and spiritual knowledge.

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